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PART 1: FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS

Challenges encountered regarding cooperation and how Una Europa/Una.Resin has tackled or intend to tackle them

Una Europa through the Una.Resin project has ambitions to develop strategies and roadmaps that support a seamless transnational research cooperation amongst its university communities. Our institutions are uniquely diverse in the areas of scientific disciplines, research traditions and cultures, organisational set ups and resources, as well as levels of “readiness” in relation to the transformational modules. As an Alliance, this thus presents us with enormous opportunities to work collaboratively to achieve maximum impact on our focus areas of one health, cultural heritage, data science and artificial intelligence, sustainability and European studies. The strength derived from our diversity encompasses a wide and complex range of perspectives, experiences, practices and situations. Within Una.Resin, we believe this diversity and its associated interdisciplinarity are a positive driving force needed to build a common sustainable research and innovation ecosystem. Our teams have welcomed this new way of working by being open-minded as we learn to embrace and adapt to the different organisational and cultural uniqueness of each partner university. Our teams are demonstrating enthusiasm and availing their creativity to support values needed to build an innovative trusted and sustainable partnership. This is a clear demonstration of the willingness of our institutions to transform and be well positioned to provide solutions through research and innovation for the challenges of the future.

Building a complex research and innovation ecosystem takes time, effort and resources. The resultant institutional changes may be gradual but eventually realised in the long term. Our institutions being made up of a wide variety of structures, actors and traditions such as bottom-up decision making (within faculties / departments) means that actions aimed at producing institutional changes might not produce immediate and concrete added value for all stakeholders (in terms of services and opportunities). For example, convincing our researchers about spending additional time on collaborating on Human Capital, Citizen Science, Open Science, among others was a challenging task. We have and are addressing this by creating platforms and opportunities for researchers to engage in dialogue about the added values of these collaborations. The establishment of a Research Strategy Group for the Alliance – consisting of vice-rectors for research and senior colleagues from the research offices (representing positions of internal stakeholders), and tasked with supporting the development of a common R&I strategy for the Alliance beyond the realms of the Una.Resin project – has been key to keeping the focus on the added value of research collaboration within the Una Europa Alliance. This is leading to better understanding of project goals and the opportunities for growth. To ensure seamless and continuous partner engagement,

our approach to project management and how we communicate and engage with all our stakeholders will continue to evolve to meet project and present demands.

In a project of such magnitude, there is the challenge of being solely focused on the formal requirements by the funder. Our approach has been to fulfil the funder's requirements and our obligations without losing focus on the substantive changes that we envisage the outputs and outcomes of the project would generate for our partnership and our communities. In doing so, our aim is to ensure that the innovative outcomes of our project would be ground-breaking as we uphold quality assurance processes and encourage creativity within our research and professional community. For example, Una.Resin project outputs are embedded in the Una Europa ecosystem via its rollout proposal, Una.Universitas, and its Strategy 2030 policy document. We are also creating a framework that lays the foundation for consolidating activities, methods and reflections for the institutional change and the creation of concrete services and opportunities with the potential for both short- and long-term impact.

The themes of our transformation modules, according to our mapping exercises on Common Research and Innovation (R&I) agenda, Sharing Research Infrastructure and Resources, and Strengthening Human Capital Development, support the strategic aims of the individual Una Europa universities as well as the Alliance. These transformation modules are very comprehensive with wide ranging aims. However, the resources allocated to these are comparatively very limited. For this reason, the building of a cluster approach that transverses across all Work Packages took a longer time than expected to set up during the initial stages. Despite this, we have built a strong membership of key researchers and other professional staff within our six clusters who are offering their time and expertise as advisors for our project. This is an added value from our institutions and a demonstration of the commitment and the positive buy-in from our stakeholders. The continuous engagement of our cluster members is contributing to the development of each partner university and the career development of our staff as we share ideas and embrace change. Thus, our universities have looked beyond the project budget to incentivise our staff to actively engage in Una.Resin related activities such as through the establishment of schemes that compensate for teaching hours. Central to our partnership is the value we place on co-creating ideas and priorities that the Alliance aims to address. This approach provides a firm guarantee that actions and initiatives we undertake have clear added value and benefits for our members and communities.

Tangible progress made and added value by our institutions and alliance

It is important to highlight that it has only been 18 months since the Una.Resin project was set up. It might therefore be premature to understand the tangible changes that are accelerating institutional change. We are developing several practices and piloting them with relevant academics and other stakeholders. While some of our outputs may result in immediate changes, we are conscious that incremental changes would be realised during the project's lifetime and beyond. Nevertheless, we highlight some progress that are

adding value to our collaboration and contributing to changes to policies and practices at both institutional and Alliance levels.

A key tangible progress and an added value of Una Europa as an Alliance has been the establishment of expert Clusters working on the transformation modules. These working groups have enabled us to bring together academic, professional and administrative staff from diverse disciplines. This has allowed for an important institutional barrier breaking ensuring that we no longer work in silos but collaboratively and cooperatively. Cluster advisors have provided great insight into project development and delivery as well as showing strong commitment to working and sharing best practices, for example, in the areas of human capital development, and open science including citizen science, within the Alliance. This has been through the organisation of a series of webinars and in-person workshops enabling the sharing of best practices related to R&I, human capital development, open science and citizen science. Institutions have identified and appointed relatively large group of enthusiastic, committed and engaged people (academics, researchers, professional staff and students), who are devoting their time and expertise to Una.Resin and Una Europa related activities. In particular, the Una Europa academic-led Self-Steering Committees on Cultural Heritage and One Health have sought to engage with the Una.Resin activities to benefit from, e.g. the organisation of joint workshops for joint proposals to EU funding and mappings of research infrastructures. Different institutions employ different approaches to address challenges allowing for learning and flexibility of working within the Alliance. For example, some partners have developed dedicated units within their universities which are solely devoted to Una Europa collaboration. Some institutions have set up dedicated internal steering committees comprised of senior researchers, who advise on processes, engage with relevant units and communicate project aims and opportunities at the home faculties and institutes as well to the relevant stakeholders. Altogether, we are creating internal task force to work on cross-cutting transformation areas, with coordination at the research domain, technical and political levels. Through our collaboration, we are witnessing slow, but steady growth in our understanding of the similarities and differences of the organisational and research cultures across our Alliance. Our administrative, professional and support staff are also experiencing different levels of internationalisation through working collaboratively at the cluster level. There have also been fruitful exchanges between library staff, technology transfer officers and other administrative units about how knowledge exchange can be enhanced toward delivering project goals.

A joint legal entity under Belgian law was established in 2019 to build sustainable governance structures for the Una Europa Alliance, to facilitate close collaboration between the partner institutions and to develop joint strategies for long-term sustainability. To ensure strategic alignment at the level of R&I policy between the Una Europa partner universities, the Research Strategy Group has been established (as outlined above). We have seen the integration of Una.Resin aims and initial outputs into Alliance level strategies for implementation. We have explored the outcomes of our exercises to map strategic aims, policies and practices to support Una Europa R&I collaboration. The Horizon Europe programme provides many opportunities for our academics to jointly benefit from. Some joint proposals have already been developed and we are also benefitting from participation in projects with other partners, including the

RitrainPlus project around strengthening the human capital of research infrastructures. Fully embedding Una.Resin aims and outcomes in the Una Europa ecosystem has appeared as a natural and obvious need. Integrating research and education is seen within our Alliance as key drivers that have the potential to contribute to social impact and this is widely acknowledged by our stakeholders as a key priority of Una Europa's rollout proposal, Una.Universitas. The advantage is the vital importance this provides regarding Una.Resin's long-term sustainability. We are actively exploring opportunities for our research community to build holistic cooperation aimed at securing long-term funding to develop some of the initiatives arising from our project. Some partners have secured co-funding from national governments to stimulate their participation in the R&I dimension of the Alliance. These funds are used to stimulate bottom-up interaction with Una Europa partners, within the pre-defined focus areas. At the institutional level, we are witnessing resources being allocated to stimulate bottom-up interaction with (but not exclusively) Una Europa partners including the Una Europa Seed Fund, and Una Europa institutions included as partners in funding programmes such as Global PhD partnerships with selected institutes and the CELSA projects funded by the CELSA Research Fund.

There is increasing buy-in from our institutions and this is evident by the organisation of internal engagements and discussions for and with stakeholders at all levels including vice rectors, researchers, project managers and cluster members, to share on-going activities and upcoming events on a regular basis. Una Europa's One Health focus area has served as a catalyst for the internal organisation of similar One Health programmes at some partner institutions including dedicated steering committees, organisation of workshops and the prospect of undertaking large networking events in the future.

We are experiencing a growing interest around research infrastructures, connected to the activities on this transformation module undertaken by Una.Resin and based on inputs and priorities across our institutions. At some institutions, we have seen some investment on research infrastructures and the development of a centralised policy on both physical and data infrastructures, with the aim of developing research infrastructures as key drivers for promoting research excellence. A barrier-free environment aligning with FAIR principles but acknowledging discipline specific constraints, for the exchange of data, information and practices within our partnership is very crucial. Una Europa continues to provide an opportunity to scale up data access and to remove barriers in the form of regulations, finances, human resource constraints and incompatible systems.

The added value of collaborating with and being recognised by businesses and third sector parties is that all Una Europa member universities benefit from it. This experience is being used as a motivator for thinking of how business collaboration can be built within the partnership. One such initiatives is Una Europa's involvement as a key partner in the winning consortium, ICE - Innovation by Creative Economy, to set up the next Knowledge and Innovation Community (KIC) on Culture and Creativity. This consortium brings together over 50 partners from 20 countries with the mission to unlock the innovation potential of the cultural and creative sectors and industries in Europe. Una Europa is also the only higher education player in Europe to be involved in the Horizon-Europe funded ARCHE project. This project brings together national ministries or agencies to co-develop strategic research and innovation agenda for

Cultural and Creative Sector (CCS) in Europe. This agenda setting will provide an important framework for the development of the KIC and demonstrates that Una Europa already has a strong links with national ministries and strategic industries.

PART 2: POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Executive summary

The Una Europa partner universities have come together to build a **European University of the Future** with quality education and excellent research at the core. We foster an environment where innovative and critical thinking is encouraged and the boundaries of transnational collaboration are challenged, in order to drive forward the **European Higher Education and Research Areas** and make a meaningful contribution to society.

The European Universities Initiative is an entirely new and unique form of transnational collaboration – one that goes beyond traditional frameworks and existing structures and it is crucial that it is recognised and supported as such. The European Commission's commitment to providing **sustainable long-term funding** to European University Alliances is the single most important factor that will define the success of existing European University Alliances and therefore the initiative as a whole. It is critical that such a funding instrument is **competitive in nature** and always geared towards the **principles of quality, excellence and impact**. Furthermore, it must not take away from existing research and innovation funding but rather represent an additional investment at the European level that is complemented by national and regional funding sources.

This will ensure that the European Universities Initiative as a whole remains ambitious and aims high, in line with the objective of creating flagships of an innovative, globally competitive and attractive European Education Area and European Research Area. Sufficient resources remain the backbone of **European competitiveness**. In the area of research and innovation, funding is crucial to allow for the inclusion and engagement of all academic units and researchers in European University Alliances and facilitate the sharing of infrastructures and resources – from technical equipment to know-how and human resources. Furthermore, it is key that any financial support goes hand in hand with **adequate legislative and policy measures** at European, national and regional levels, in particular when it comes to the identification and removal of barriers to transnational collaboration. For research and innovation, this concerns in particular, the interoperability of Research Infrastructure and Resources, IP sharing rules, ethical regulations as well as legal Human Resource frameworks.

To solve the great global and societal challenges of our time, the Una Europa partner universities believe in the importance of **openness to the world** and collaboration with like-minded partners across the globe. The **United Kingdom and Switzerland** count some of the most international and excellent universities – many of them long-standing and close partners of higher education institutions across Europe. Close research collaboration with these partners will not only remain key to the success of both the European Higher Education Area and the European Research Area but affect our shared future.

1. Recommendations for facilitating transnational cooperation

Una Europa supports the European Commission's increased focus on facilitating transnational cooperation among higher education institutions across Europe. The Una Europa partner universities have come together to enhance the quality of education and excellence in research with the aim of pushing the boundaries of what is feasible in transnational collaboration and thereby making a **meaningful contribution to society**.

The European Universities Initiative is a completely new and unique form of transnational collaboration – one that goes beyond traditional frameworks and existing structures and it is crucial that it is supported and recognised as such. The European Commission's commitment to providing **sustainable long-term funding** to European University Alliances is one of the most important factors that will define the success of the existing European University Alliances and therefore the initiative as a whole. In our view, this funding should not only be proportionate to the strategic objectives and reflect the scope of activities proposed, but importantly take a **holistic approach**, covering education, research and innovation activities in support of higher education's ultimate mission of serving society. It is essential that the initiative remains **ambitious**, in line with the initial idea of creating flagships of an innovative, globally competitive and attractive European Education Area and European Research Area. Alliances must not be faced with too many top-down requirements, both in terms of strategic policy objective and concrete tasks but focus should always remain on the **quality and impact of outputs**.

The active engagement of the **joint community of students, professional staff and academics across our campuses** is central to the success of the European University Alliances. To achieve this, incentives are needed, in particular, **bottom-up funding for research consortia** to promote research collaboration. Furthermore, **adequate time to develop effective, impactful and sustainable ecosystems** across the Alliance's partners should be a top priority. Similarly, it is equally important to highlight that **adequate financial, human resources and political commitment** in research and innovation are a prerequisite for sharing capacities and infrastructures, which is where supportive action is needed to start with.

Any funding support should be accompanied by policy support. In particular, this concerns the **identification and removal of legal barriers**, such as interoperability of RIRs, IP sharing rules, ethical regulations as well as legal HR frameworks. This should build on the European Commission's proposals in the Council Recommendation to facilitate transnational collaboration between universities and further strengthened together in dialogue with national policymakers, representatives of European University Alliances and the higher education sector at large.

In the framework of the Una.Resin project, we expect to develop a number of strategies, policies and pilot initiatives that have the potential to lead to tangible progress and changes to the way we collaborate both

within and outside the Una Europa Alliance. It is crucial that the European Commission dedicates adequate funding aimed **at translating policies generated through these projects into practice.**

The Una Europa partner universities are very large research-intensive universities that collaborate in various ways both in Europe and internationally. However important, collaboration in the framework of a European University Alliance remains one route of transnational collaboration for the Una Europa partner universities, which is why we advocate that transnational cooperation – both in Europe and globally – is boosted and supported in the broadest sense possible.

2. Recommendations for strengthening careers

First and foremost, it is important to note that academic career assessment is not a homogenous system across the European Union. This also applies to Una Europa, where academic career assessment is one of the issues, where some of the biggest differences exist between the respective national and institutional frameworks that the Una Europa partner universities operate in. It is crucial that any reform of the academic career assessment system takes this knowledge as a starting point and avoids pushing those higher education institutions that already have more flexible and qualitative career assessments into systems that might be less advanced, in an attempt to harmonise practices.

First and foremost, **enablers for academic career development** need to be assessed and recognised, setting **diversity and equality among the targets.** In addition to ensuring a better **balance between quantitative and qualitative aspects,** it is important that academic job performance is looked at more holistically. This not only concerns the obvious research and teaching activities but includes recognition for cooperation with business and the third sector, outreach to society as well as citizen science and science communication. For this, adequate new assessment tools must be developed. Furthermore, two different objectives of academic career assessment should be clearly distinguished in the process: on the one hand, the aim of measuring an academic's performance against the performance of others; on the other hand, the aim of helping the employee unlock their full potential and further develop their career in light of their individual circumstances and aspirations.

Any attempt of solving the precariousness of early career researchers in Europe should take a **broad and holistic approach,** looking across the different issues that exist today. A mapping exercise conducted within the Una.Resin project suggests that a **broader view and re-invention of academic career paths, including the development of a fairer performance assessment procedure** is needed, which is not only limited to early career researchers but academics at all stages of their careers. This proposal is in line with the recent paper of the League of Research-Intensive Universities (LERU) on “A Pathway towards Multidimensional Academic Careers - A LERU Framework for the Assessment of Researchers”.

- Firstly, the results of our mapping on human capital development show that researchers are much more reliant on **administrative support**. The support in question must reach beyond basic needs and cover more complex aspects, such as guidance on different career paths and continuous consultation services based on individual needs of researchers.
- Secondly, a more **diverse choice of career paths** is urgently needed in Europe, one that is not limited merely to different combinations of research and teaching activities. In particular, career paths concentrated on research or teaching in cooperation with ecosystems (businesses, non-for-profit, public sector) should be developed and implemented. Universities are well placed to address this challenge, and future policy and funding instruments should be shaped to support them in this role.
- Thirdly, a **meaningful model for interdisciplinary research careers** should be developed. As it currently stands, interdisciplinarity is often an empty phrase: all actors in the interdisciplinary research ecosystem continue to face barriers that need to be overcome (e.g., joint appointments within institutions, inadequate evaluation of research proposals by funding organisations).

When it comes to the introduction of a **tenure track system at European level**, this is something that needs to be carefully examined in close collaboration with Member States. Importantly, these discussions should be based on lessons learned from countries that are currently piloting and experimenting with tenure track schemes, such as France, Germany and Switzerland. As mentioned above, we do not believe that the introduction of a tenure track system at European level alone would solve the issues related to the precariousness of early career researchers in Europe. Instead, actions proposed within the **European Strategy for Universities to future-proof skills**, for example, could provide an alternative under the condition that research assessments are adjusted to ensure equal opportunities for researchers from all scientific disciplines in bottom-up competitive and investigator-driven funding schemes, such as ERC grants or MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships.

3. Recommendations for the digital transition

European University Alliances are committed to embracing the role of higher education institutions as drivers of the digital transition in Europe. In this respect, it is important to highlight that **data sharing, data protection and data management** count among some of the most complex obstacles that Alliances are facing today. These issues are particularly difficult to overcome in the framework of research collaboration, when it comes to sensitive areas, such as health and clinical data. At this stage, data regulations at EU level led to a **competitive disadvantage** for higher education institutions and research institutes based in Europe, compared to counterparts in the US or China, with certain data. This situation is further complicated by the current lack of harmonization between national, EU and international regulations. Una Europa provides promising opportunities to increase the scale of data access, but in order to achieve this, **barriers in the form of regulations, finances and incompatible systems** need to be removed. At the same time, **work on data infrastructures sharing**, in line with ERA priority actions 1

and 8, is needed in terms of principles, guidelines and solutions on how to overcome those barriers, in particular related to interoperability and openness, regulatory constraints, IP rules etc.

Furthermore, it is crucial that **support is provided to the community of non-professionals**, in particular citizens and civil society, who will not only use but also co-develop digital tools and, even beyond, research infrastructures. In this regard, the ERA priority action 14 is an important step but would need to go further, to ensure **active and substantial engagement with civil society and citizens**. This action should also be complemented by the development of structural formats and frameworks related to digital skills, in line with ERA priority action 13, in particular, looking at large scale mobility opportunities and more flexible and innovative learning pathways.

When it comes to the development of new additional e-infrastructures at European level, it is important that the following principles should be considered:

- The **added value of the systems for science and scientists** must always remain at the centre of the endeavour.
- **Exchange across different disciplines and research ecosystems** should be enabled and encouraged.
- Overhead should be kept as simple as possible and the disruption of data owners should be kept at a minimum.
- Ensuring interoperability with existing data Research Infrastructures (large-scale and small-scale ones), at policy as well as operational level.

4. Recommendations for access to excellence

Una Europa is committed to piloting and testing formats for the benefit of all higher education institutions across Europe. All activities within Una Europa are developed with a view to sharing and scaling them with partners across Europe and the globe.

Excellence in science and value-creation is driven by the **principles of openness and collaboration**. The **sharing of research infrastructures and resources** – from technical equipment to know-how and human resources – is the very basis of achieving excellence in science. This is strongly linked to the **creation of a culture of collaboration**, where working together is encouraged and valued accordingly, and a **supportive environment**, where the individual researchers are supported to unlock their full potential and creativity. Furthermore, this should be further complemented by **support of Open Science in all its dimensions**, including Open Education, Open Data, Open Access, Citizen Science, Open Innovation. At the same time, a mapping exercise of the human capital development conducted within Una.Resin suggests a strong link to the **individual's well-being**, which is an area where more work needs to be done.

Excellent research is **international and curiosity driven** by nature. Una Europa, at its very core, has come together to create a truly European inter-university environment, where outstanding research is continuously linked to transnational learning and innovative. The Una Europa partner universities share a joint commitment to **challenge-based multidisciplinary research of the future**, however, there are currently numerous barriers for researchers on the ground.

Concretely, we believe the following actions can improve access to excellence across Europe:

- **Increased recognition and support for inter- and multidisciplinary research**
 - Introduction of inter- and multidisciplinary approaches in national and international evaluation and assessment processes;
 - Bottom-up funding instruments for challenge-based multidisciplinary research as well as support basic research of which the added value for society may not be immediate, but which may be critical in solving societal challenges in the future;
 - Introduction of new criteria for the publication of challenge-based multidisciplinary research;
 - Support for societal outreach activities and business-academia collaboration;
 - Development of new career paths focusing on inter- and multidisciplinary research.
- **Funding and structures to facilitate the inclusion of all academic units of the universities:** for the long-term success of the European University Alliances, it is crucial that funding is sufficient to allow all levels of the university to be involved and benefit from the added value of the initiative.
- **Incentives and rewards for researchers:** increased incentives and rewards are needed for researchers, i.e. via seed funding schemes.
- **Mobility:** mobility is a key enabler. Broad mobility pathways for all, from early-career researchers to senior academics, is an effective way to encourage research collaboration and provide access to excellence and create new knowledge and added-value in Europe. Going forward, funding for the European Universities Initiative should include sufficient funding for such a mobility strategy, also including digital mobility of researchers.

5. Recommendations for increasing global competitiveness

To tackle (solve) the great **global and societal challenges** of our time, the Una Europa partner universities believe in **collaboration with like-minded partners across the globe**, following challenge-based and multidisciplinary approaches. In particular, Una Europa is focusing on engagement **with research-intensive universities from across the African continent**, following Una Europa's commitment to developing **meaningful, complex and long-lasting partnership** with global partners. Such partnerships are essential to developing research and outreach activities which create impact at scale.

The backbone of **European competitiveness** is sufficient resources. While the funding allocated in the pilot phase of the European Universities Initiative has been key to establishing the Alliance's first collaborative activities, it is important to highlight that true value and impact at scale can only be guaranteed by **significant and long-term sustainable funding solutions and equitable research collaboration across partners**. At the same time, funding for European Universities should not turn into thematic funding, thus adding further top-down requirements onto the Alliances. Future funding should be flexible in nature and allow each Alliance to develop its particular strengths to benefit the whole world. The existing European University Alliances are incredibly diverse, which is something that should be nurtured as a key strength of the initiative in the long-term. While we recognise the importance of strategic policy objectives for the European Universities Initiative, these must never undo the **strategic visions and objectives of individual Alliances**.

When it comes to driving the international competitiveness of the European higher education sector as a whole, we believe there should be an increased focus on **Europe's distinctiveness and unique role in the world**. For example, a competitive advantage might be achieved by a strong emphasis on the well-being of researchers, the careful development of research environments, where researchers are free to safely pursue their interest free from outside interference as well as a focus on the specific **European values** that will set the ERA aside from other research landscapes. Furthermore, Europe – and by extension Europe's higher education sector – are incredibly diverse – rather than seeing this as a challenge, this **diversity should be turned into a strategic asset**. Close research collaboration with like-minded partners across the globe should be encouraged – the **United Kingdom** and **Switzerland** in particular count some of the most international and excellent universities, which will remain important partners for the long-term success of both the European Higher Education Area and the European Research Area.

Specifically, global competitiveness of Europe's higher education sector will be boosted by:

- Supporting international cooperation by increasing the dedicated instruments/ bottom-up actions that are as open as possible;
- Encouraging mobility, internships and international visits on a global scale for students, researchers as well as professional staff;
- Increasing mobility opportunities by harmonising practices related to visa and work permits for students, recent graduates as well as academics from outside the European Union;
- Funding interdisciplinary, challenge-based approaches that go beyond capacity-building within the European Excellence Initiative, developing a solid benchmarking process against which to measure international competitiveness and excellence.